

FABRICATION PROCESS AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF VGCNFS/AL COMPOSITES BY SPARK SINTERING

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1 Introduction

Recently, carbon/Al composites have been grate watched because of the application of heat-sink for semi-conductor. This composite seems to have good thermal conductivity and adequate thermal expansion. But this composite has been still use practically, which is caused by the low wettability between carbon and Al, and the high reactivity at interface. These properties are depend on the surface structure of carbon, but many carbon has different surface structure. The vapor-grown carbon nano fibers (VGCNFs) has been expected as an ideal reinforcement for Al matrix composites in order to improve the mechanical and thermal properties of matrix materials because of their excellent mechanical, electrical and thermal properties ^[1, 2]. Furthermore, the interface between carbon and aluminum in VGCNF/Al composites has low reactivity compared with other conventional carbon fibers during fabrication process, because the surface of VGCNFs is covered with c- plain completely and has low defect density ^[3]. The control of VGCNFs dispersion in VGCNFs/Al composites is very difficult because of the aggregation, higher aspect ratio and specific surface area of VGCNFs. Usually raw VGCNF supplied from company agglutinate. As a result, the mixing process of VGCNFs and Al powder is very important for the fabrication of VGCNFs/Al composites with control of VGCNFs dispersion. But, the influence of different dispersion of VGCNFs in Al matrix on the mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of composites has not yet been clarified.

In this study, the spark sintering (SS) process was used to fabricate VGCNFs/Al composites in order to control the dispersion of reinforcements in matrix because of no segregation of component during powder metallurgy (PM) process. And, the sintering

rate of VGCNFs/Al composite during spark sintering, the microstructure and the strength of VGCNFs/Al composites was also investigated.

2 Experimental Procedures

VGCNFs used were offered by Showa Denko Co. in Japan, which forms 0.15-0.2 μ m and 10-20 μ m for average diameter and fiber length, respectively. Pure Al powders with 99.95% in purity and with different average diameters with 1, 3, and 30 μ m were used as matrix.

VGCNFs and Al powder was mixed as follows; VGCNFs are dipped in the dispersion solution with ultrasonic vibration (45 KHz) for 1 h in order to disperse VGCNFs uniformly in the dispersion solution. The acetone, ethanol and butanol were used as dispersion solution. Subsequently, Al powders are added into it. The mixed VGCNFs and Al powder solutions were dispersed by the mechanical stirring assisted with ultrasonic vibration for 1 h. Further, the mixed solution is milled in jars with alumina ball at 50 rpm for 18 h, and is dried at room temperature. The mixed powders were spark sintered for 0.6 ks with a pulse current of 100 ampere (A), and a pulse-discharge time and pulse-cut time of 100 ms, and punch pressure of 15 MPa. The mixed powders were heated to fixed maximum temperatures at 823-833 K for 1.8 ks under an applied uniaxial punch pressure of 50 MPa after the pulsed electrical discharge. The relationship between relative density and densification speed during SS for monolithic aluminum powder and the mixture powders of VGCNFs and Al was investigated. The microstructures of composites were observed by an optical microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM). Finally, the size of Al powder on tensile strength of composites was estimated by

using a tensile testing machine with a constant crosshead speed of $2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

3 Results and Discussion

In order to investigate the suitable dispersion solution in wet mixing process, the segmentation speed of Al particles was examined for acetone, ethanol and butanol, which has same density ($0.79\text{-}0.81 \times 10^3 \text{ g/m}^3$) and different viscosity, 0.31 g s/m , 1.05 g s/m and 3 g s/m , respectively. Fig. 1 shows the sedimentation speed of Al particle with diameter of $30 \mu\text{m}$ in different dispersion solutions. The sedimentation speed of Al particle in ethanol and butanol are one third and one eighth of that in acetone, respectively. Segmentation speed is proposal to viscosity of solution, strongly. Consequently, ethanol and butanol is suitable for dispersion solution in mixing process of VGCNFs and Al powder because of slow segmentation speed for easy handling.

Fig. 1 Sedimentation speed of $30 \mu\text{m}$ Al powders in the different dispersion solution.

Fig. 2 shows microstructure of mixed powder of VGCNF and Al particles with diameter of $30 \mu\text{m}$ for each dispersion solutions. Fraction of VGCNF is 10 % in volume. Although partial Al particle inserted into the aggregation of VGCNFs, the aggregation of VGCNFs is not disentangled completely after wet mixing in acetone and ethanol. On the other hand, VGCNFs are disentangled completely after wet mixing in butanol. This demonstrated that the viscosity of dispersion solution facilitated the uniform dispersion of VGCNFs in Al powder during the wet mixing. Butanol is suitable solution for the dispersion of

VGCNF. But as the dry speed of butanol solution is very slow. As time of dry process for the mixture of VGCNFs and butanol is over 5 days, ethanol was used for subsequent experiments.

Fig.2 SEM images of 10 vol.% VGCNFs/Al mixture by wet mixing process with $30 \mu\text{m}$ Al powder in (a) acetone, (b) ethanol and (c) butanol solution, respectively.

As segmentation speed of Al powders in solution is proportional to square of the diameter of powders, fine particles is suitable for the mixing of VGCNFs and Al powders. Fig. 3 shows microstructure of 10 vol. % VGCNF and Al powder mixtures with different diameter of Al powders mixed by wet

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mixing in ethanol. The spherical particles and needle-like in Figs. 3 (a) and 3 (b) are Al and VGCNFs, respectively. VGCNFs are dispersed uniformly in the Al powder matrix with 1 μm and 3 μm Al powders. However, an obvious aggregation of VGCNFs is observed in VGCNFs/30 μm Al mixture, as shown in Fig. 3 (c).

Fig.3 SEM images of 10 vol.% VGCNFS/Al mixture mixed using (a) 1 μm Al powders, (b) 3 μm Al powders and (c) 30 μm Al powders, respectively.

Fig.4 Comparison of densification rate between pure Al compact and 10 vol. % VGCNFS/ Al composite.

Then, the optimization of fabrication conditions of composites by SS process was examined. All composites have high density above 98.5% after sintering. Fig. 4 shows the densification rate between pure Al compact and 10 vol. % VGCNF/ Al composite with 1 μm Al powders. Densification rate of pure Al and composite increased with increasing relative density in the early stage of small relative density. In other words, there were maximum values of densification rate at relative density of 0.725 for composite. Afterwards, Densification rate of composite decreases with increasing relative density. This behavior is very similar to that of the monolithic alloy. This indicates the densification rate of VGCNFS/Al composite powder depended on Al powder for matrix, but independent on VGCNFS.

Fig. 5 shows the optical images of the composites fabricated by using Al powders with different average diameters. In these figures, the gray region with flat area and black region with needle-like image are Al and carbon, respectively. Fig. 5 (a) shows the microstructures of VGCNFS/1 μm Al composite. It shows that the VGCNFS are dispersed uniformly in Al matrix. However, in VGCNFS/30 μm Al composite, an obvious aggregation of the VGCNFS is observed. Aggregated VGCNFS filled in the interspaces between the Al particles as shown in Fig. 5 (c). Moreover, aggregation of VGCNFS exhibited a preferential orientation, which results from the deformation of Al powders under the uniaxial pressure during the hot pressing.

Fig.5 Optical micrographs of 10 vol. % VGCNFs/Al composites fabricated using (a) 1 μm Al powders, (c) 3 μm Al powders and (e) 30 μm Al powders, respectively; (b), (d) and (f) are the SEM images of (a), (c) and (e), respectively.

Fig.6 Tensile strength of the VGCNFs/Al composites and the corresponding Al blocks fabricated using different diameter of Al particles. The inset table shows the increment rate of tensile strength of the composite relative to that of Al block.

Fig. 6 shows the tensile strength of VGCNFs/Al composites and monolithic Al blocks. The tensile strength of Al blocks increased with decreasing the diameter of Al particles, which is caused by the

grain refinement of Al matrix. On the other hand, the tensile strength of VGCNFs/Al composites is higher than that of the corresponding Al blocks because of the effect of reinforcement by VGCNFs. The increasing rate of the tensile strength of composites for the corresponding Al blocks increased with decreasing the diameter of Al particles. The increasing rate of the tensile strength of composites with respect to the corresponding Al blocks was 4.7 times for VGCNFs/1 μm Al composite, 3.6 times for VGCNFs/3 μm Al composite and 1.5 times for the VGCNFs/30 μm Al composite, respectively. It seems the increasing rate of the tensile strength of the composites is also closely related to the dispersion of VGCNFs in the Al matrix. Since VGCNFs in Al matrix aggregated increasingly with increasing the diameter of Al particles, the interface area between VGCNFs and Al matrix decreased. Moreover, the weak bonding between VGCNFs in aggregation of VGCNFs also reduced to the tensile strength of composites. As a result, the reinforcement effect of VGCNFs is decreased in the composites.

4 Conclusions

Suitable fabrication process of 10 vol % VGCNFs/Al composites was investigated, from the view point of the distribution of VGCFs in Al matrix. Following is our conclusions;

Butanol had low segmentation speed for al powders and suitable for good dispersion of VGCF in Al particles. But butanol needs long drying time, compared with acetone and ethanol. As decreasing the mean size of Al powder, VGCNF became to distribute uniformly.

So that, VGCNFs/Al mixture of uniform dispersion of 10 vol. % VGCNFs in Al powder with diameter of 1 μm were obtained by wet mixing in ethanol.

The densification rate of VGCNFs/Al composite powder depended on Al powder for matrix, but independent on VGCNFs.

10 vol. % VGCNFs/Al composites are fabricated by SS as a function of the diameter of Al powders. VGCNFs are dispersed uniformly in the VGCNFs/1 μm Al composite, but the aggregations of VGCNFs exhibited a preferential orientation.

Tensile strength of the Al blocks was improved by adding 10vol% VGCNF. As decreasing size of Al powders, the tensile strength of the composites was improved dramatically.

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